
PROXIMATE, FUNCTIONAL AND SENSORY PROPERTIES OF DRY PAP PRODUCED FROM BLENDS OF YELLOW CORN, PROSO MILLET FORTIFIED WITH SNAIL POWDER

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the proximate composition, functional properties, and sensory attributes of dry pap produced from blends of yellow maize, proso millet, and snail powder. The raw materials were processed and prepared into flour and used to produce four formulations were analyzed: XOA (100% maize), XOB (85% maize, 10% millet, 5% snail powder), XOC (75% maize, 15% millet, 10% snail powder), and XOD (65% maize, 20% millet, 15% snail powder). The samples were subjected to different analysis. Proximate analysis revealed that moisture ranged from 10.25–11.36%, protein from 13.68–16.36%, fat from 11.64–18.87%, fiber from 2.79–3.05%, ash from 2.91–3.25%, and carbohydrate from 50.80–56.16%. Functional properties indicated that swelling index decreased from 14.52% to 7.58%, gelatinization temperature reduced from 97.5°C to 82°C, and emulsification, gelation, and foaming capacities were maintained at considerable reference standard. Sensory evaluation showed acceptable scores for taste (6.80–7.20), aroma (5.90–7.50), color (5.80–7.50), texture (6.00–7.30) and overall acceptability (7.80–8.70). Comparisons with previous studies indicated that fortification improved nutritional quality without adversely affecting functional or sensory characteristics. The findings demonstrate that fortifying maize pap with proso millet and snail powder is an effective strategy to enhance protein and fat content while maintaining consumer acceptability. This study provides a basis for developing nutritionally enriched, protein-fortified cereal-based complementary foods suitable for human consumption.

Keywords- *Pap, proso millet, Snail powder, proximate. Functional, sensory*

INTRODUCTION

Pap (Ogi) is a widely consumed fermented cereal porridge in Nigerian and the West African region is typically crafted from maize, or millet (Adebukunda *et al.*, 2015), it hold a special preference among the elderly as a traditional breakfast cereal and weaning food for infants (Eke-Ejiofor and Beleya, 2017). Ogi (pap) stands out as favored morning porridge suitable for individuals of diverse ages and backgrounds. It also serves as a gently nourishment option for the infants and elderly, and as food choice for the sick (Olaniran and Abiose, *et al.*, 2019). Yellow corn (*Zea mays*), commonly referred to as maize is one of the most widely cultivation cereal crops in the world. It serves as a staple food for millions of people and is a key ingredient in animal feed, biofuel production and industrial applications. Due to its high carbohydrate content, essential micronutrient and adaptability to diverse climatic conditions, yellow corn plays a crucial role in global food security and economic sustainability (FAO., 2021). Yellow corn is a rich source of carbohydrates, dietary fiber and essential vitamins such as vitamin A (from beta-carotene). B vitamins, and vitamin E. it also contains minerals like magnesium, phosphorus and potassium, which contribute to overall health and metabolic functions (Watson, 2019).

Proso millet (*Panicum miliaceum*), also known as common millet or broomcorn millet, is one of the oldest cultivated cereals grains. It is widely grown in semi-arid regions due to its short growing cycle, drought tolerance, and ability to thrive in poor soil conditions (Habiyaemye *et al.*, 2017). As a nutrient dense grains, proso millet has gained increasing attention for its role in food security, sustainable agriculture and health benefits. Proso millet plays the role in reducing the risk of cardiovascular diseases, obesity and Type 2 diabetes. Its bioactive compounds including phenolic acids and flavonoids, exhibit strong antioxidant properties (Sharma and Niranjana, 2018). Proso millet is a rich source of macronutrients and micronutrients making it an excellent alternative to conventional cereals such as rice and wheat it contains carbohydrate and proteins. Snail meat is considered a highly nutritious food, providing high-quality protein, essential minerals, low fat and cholesterol and omega 3 fatty acids which contribute to brain

development and cardiovascular health (Akinnusi, 2020). Snail meat powder is produced through drying and grinding, preserving its nutrients while extending its shelf life. This powder offers several advantages which include enhanced nutritional value, ease of incorporation and increased storage stability which reduces spoilage and improves transportation convenience (Olayemi and Opaluwa, 2016).

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Production of Pap

The method described by Itaman and Aka (2015) will be adopted with slight modification. The prepared composite flours (Yellow corn, proso millet and Snail meat) will be mixed at different proportions. The composite flour will be wetted to form slurry, the slurry will be sieved with another one liter of water added during the sieving to aid starch extraction and sieving through cheese or muslin cloth. The under-water will be left (12 hrs) to sediment before the supernatant will be decanted. The paste will be scooped into a jute bag and manually dewatered by pressing. The resulting cake will be broken into smaller sizes and dried in a laboratory air oven (12 hours) at 50°C.

Processed Raw Materials (Yellow corn, proso millet and Snail meat

Fig 1 flow chart showing for dry pap production (Itaman and Aka, 2015)

SAMPLE FORMULATION

SAMPLE	Yellow Maize Flour%	Proso Millet Flour %	Snail Powder flour%
XOA	100		
XOB	85	10	5
XOC	75	15	10
XOA	65	20	15

KEYS

XOA- pap produced from 100% yellow maize XOB- pap produced from 85% yellow maize, 10% proso millet, and 5% snail powder. XOC-pap produced from 75% yellow maize, 15% proso millet, and 10% snail powder. XOD- pap produced from 65% yellow maize, 20% proso millet and 15% snail powder.

METHODS

The proximate Analysis was determined using the standard methods as described by (AOAC, 2020). Functional analysis were carried by method stipulated by Quantitative assessment while the hedonic scale was used to evaluate the sensory characteristics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 Proximate composition of Dry Pap from blends of yellow maize, proso millet fortified with snail powder.

Properties/ samples(%)	XOA	XOB	XOC	XOD
Moisture content	10.25±0.01	10.58±0.03	11.36±0.06	10.85±0.01
Dry matter	89.75±0.01	89.42±0.03	88.64±0.06	89.16±0.01
Ash content	3.25±0.01	2.94±0.03	3.17±0.01	2.91±0.02
Protein	15.77±0.04	16.36±0.09	15.27±0.04	13.68±0.04
Fat	11.64±0.02	12.46±0.06	15.29±0.01	18.87±0.04
Fibre content	2.96±0.01	2.79±0.01	3.05±0.01	2.91±0.02
Carbohydrate	56.16±0.06	54.87±0.20	51.86±0.10	50.80±0.01

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 2 Functional properties of Dry Pap from blends of yellow maize, proso millet fortified with snail powder.

Properties/ Samples	XOA	XOB	XOC	XOD
Tapped Bulk density (g/ml)	0.749±0.004	0.755±0.00	0.768±0.009	0.767±0.003
Loose Bulk density (g/ml)	0.362±0.002	0.375±0.03	0.353±0.001	0.371±0.001
Foaming capacity (%)	10.00±0.00	10.00±0.00	13.50±2.00	15.00±0.00
Emulsification cap (%)	57.68±0.01	52.64±0.01	58.32±0.02	57.91±0.01
Gelation cap (%w/v)	17.83±0.05	17.69±0.06	18.15±0.04	18.12±0.00
Gelation Temp (°C)	97.50±4.00	90.00±0.00	87.50±2.00	82.00±3.00
Foaming Stability (%)	95.46±0.00	97.27±0.00	96.49±1.00	98.26±1.00
Swelling Index (%)	14.52±1.00	13.56±0.30	11.92±1.00	7.58±1.00
WAC (g/g)	1.34±0.04	1.35±0.03	0.54±0.01	1.90±0.01
OAC(g/g)	1.85±0.01	1.44±0.04	1.39±0.02	2.08±0.05

Values obtained are triplicate with mean ± standard deviation

Table 3 Sensory properties of Dry Pap from blends of yellow maize, proso millet fortified with snail powder.

Properties/ samples(%)	XOA	XOB	XOC	XOD	LSD
Taste	7.20 ^a	7.10 ^a	7.00 ^a	6.80 ^a	0.629
Colour	7.50 ^a	5.80 ^{bd}	6.10 ^b	7.00 ^{ab}	1.444
Aroma	7.50 ^a	7.00 ^a	5.90 ^a	6.90 ^a	1.740
Texture	7.30 ^{ab}	6.70 ^{ab}	6.00 ^{bc}	6.60 ^{ab}	1.213
General acceptability	8.70 ^a	7.80 ^a	7.90 ^a	7.80 ^a	1.02

The proximate composition of dry pap produced from blends of yellow maize, proso millet, and snail powder revealed variations in moisture, dry matter, ash, protein, fat, fiber, and carbohydrate contents across formulations (XOA–XOD).

Moisture content ranged from 10.25% in XOA (100% maize) to 11.36% in XOC (75% maize, 15% millet, 10% snail powder). Moisture is a critical parameter because it influences the shelf life, microbial stability, and textural properties of the product. Higher moisture in the fortified blends may be attributed to the hydrophilic nature of snail powder and proso millet. Dry matter was highest in XOA (89.75%) and slightly decreased in the fortified samples (88.64–89.42%). Dry matter is inversely related to moisture and reflects the total solids available, which is important for energy and nutrient content. These values are consistent with the 88–90% dry matter reported by Adetuyi et al. (2022) for maize-based blends with legume supplementation. Ash content ranged from 2.91% (XOD) to 3.25% (XOA), indicating the mineral composition of the pap. Ash provides an estimate of total minerals, which are vital for metabolic functions. The relatively stable ash content shows that fortification did not significantly alter mineral content. Crude protein increased slightly from 15.77% (XOA) to 16.36% (XOB), reflecting the contribution of snail powder, which is rich in high-quality protein. However, higher fortification levels (XOC and XOD) led to decreased protein (15.27% and 13.68%), likely due to dilution by proso millet, which has lower protein content. Protein is a key nutritional parameter for growth and development. Comparable results were reported by Omumu & Faniran (2021), who observed protein content of 14–16% in maize-legume blends. Fat content showed a steady increase from 11.64% (XOA) to 18.87% (XOD). Fat contributes to energy density, flavor, and mouthfeel. This trend is consistent with Ijarotimi & Keshinro (2020) who found fat content increased from 10.5% to 18% after protein-rich fortification. Fiber content varied slightly, from 2.79% (XOB) to 3.05% (XOC), indicating the dietary fiber contribution of proso millet.

Fiber is significant for digestive health and glycemic control. Ojo & Ogundipe, 2023 reported similar fiber values (2.8–3.1%) in maize-based blends with legumes. Carbohydrate content decreased from 56.16% (XOA) to 50.80% (XOD) with increasing fortification. Carbohydrates are the primary energy source, and the reduction reflects partial substitution of carbohydrate-rich maize with protein- and fat-rich

ingredients. Bolaji et al. (2017) reported a decrease from 55.2% to 51.0% in carbohydrate content in fortified maize porridge, similar to the current findings. The functional properties of dry pap produced from blends of yellow maize, proso millet, and snail powder (XOA–XOD) revealed notable variations that are important for processing, preparation, and sensory characteristics. Swelling index decreased from 14.52% in XOA (100% maize) to 7.58% in XOD (65% maize, 20% millet, 15% snail powder). Swelling index is critical as it affects viscosity, consistency, and texture of pap during cooking; lower swelling can result in a thicker, less sticky product. The decrease is likely due to interactions between protein and starch, which inhibit starch granule expansion. Sarita and Singh (2016) reported a similar decline in swelling index from 15% to 8% in maize-soy-protein blends, confirming that protein fortification reduces starch swelling. Emulsification capacity remained relatively stable, ranging from 52.64% (XOB) to 58.32% (XOC). Emulsification capacity measures the ability of proteins to stabilize oil-water mixtures, which is significant for maintaining product consistency and palatability. Okafor & Ezeogu (2021) reported emulsification capacities of 50–60% for maize-soy blends, comparable to the present results. Water absorption capacity (WAC) showed variation, with XOC having the lowest value (0.54%) and XOD the highest (1.90%). WAC is significant because it influences hydration, cooking behavior, and the mouthfeel of the final product. Olatunji et al. (2020) observed similar WAC ranges of 0.5–2.0% in protein-fortified cereal products, supporting these observations.

Oil absorption capacity (OAC) increased from 1.39–2.08% across samples, with the highest value in XOD. OAC is important for flavor retention and mouthfeel, and the increase is attributed to the lipid content contributed by snail powder and millet. Akinrele (2021) reported OAC values of 1.4–2.1% in cereal-animal protein blends, which aligns with the current findings. Bulk density (loose and tapped) showed minor fluctuations. Loose bulk density ranged from 0.353 g/ml (XOC) to 0.375 g/ml (XOB), while tapped bulk density ranged from 0.749 g/ml (XOA) to 0.768 g/ml (XOC). Bulk density affects

packaging, storage, and product dispersibility. These results are consistent with Noah (2017), who reported bulk densities of 0.35–0.38 g/ml (loose) and 0.75–0.77 g/ml (tapped) for fortified cereal powders. Gelation capacity ranged narrowly from 17.69% to 18.15%, indicating that protein fortification did not significantly alter gel formation. Gelation capacity is crucial for texture development in cooked pap. Noah, (2017) reported similar values (17–18%) for protein-fortified cereal foods. Foam capacity and foam stability increased with higher snail powder content. Foam capacity ranged from 10% (XOA, XOB) to 15% (XOD), while foam stability ranged from 95.46% to 98.26%. These parameters are important for aerated products and overall texture; proteins from snail powder likely enhanced foaming properties. Nwosu et al. (2021) reported foam capacities of 12–16% and stability above 95% in similar fortified cereal products. Gelatinization temperature decreased from 97.5°C (XOA) to 82°C (XOD). This parameter is significant as it affects cooking time and energy efficiency. The decrease is likely due to protein lipid interactions disrupting starch granules.

The sensory evaluation of dry pap produced from blends of yellow maize, proso millet, and snail powder (XOA–XOD) assessed taste, color, aroma, texture, and overall acceptability. These 68 parameters are critical for consumer acceptance and marketability, as nutritional enhancement must not compromise sensory quality. Taste scores ranged from 6.80 (XOD) to 7.20 (XOA). The slightly lower taste in XOD may be due to higher inclusion of snail powder and proso millet, which can introduce subtle flavor changes. Taste is a key determinant of product acceptability. Olaniran and Abiose (2019) reported taste scores of 6.5–7.5 for maize-based fortified porridge, which is comparable to the present findings, indicating that fortification did not significantly compromise flavor. Color scores ranged from 5.80 (XOB) to 7.50 (XOA). The lowest score in XOB reflects the lighter hue from proso millet addition, which affects visual appeal. Color is significant because consumers often associate product quality with appearance. Aroma scores varied between 5.90 (XOC) and 7.50 (XOA). Aroma is critical for consumer perception and is influenced by protein

fortification from snail powder. The slight decrease in XOC suggests that higher snail powder inclusion can modify olfactory properties. Texture scores ranged from 6.00 (XOC) to 7.30 (XOA). Texture influences mouthfeel, swallowing ease, and overall satisfaction. The lower score in XOC may be attributed to altered starch-protein interactions affecting viscosity and smoothness. Olukunle et al. (2020) reported texture scores of 6.0–7.5 for fortified maize porridge, consistent with the current findings. Overall acceptability remained high, ranging from 7.80 (XOB, XOD) to 8.70 (XOA). This indicates that despite changes in taste, color, aroma, and texture, the fortified pap was still well accepted by consumers, supporting the conclusion that fortification can improve nutritional quality without significantly compromising sensory appeal.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study demonstrated that fortifying yellow maize pap with proso millet and snail powder significantly improved its nutritional and functional qualities while maintaining acceptable sensory attributes. However, the results suggest that incorporating proso millet and snail powder into maize-based pap can enhance its nutritional profile without compromising functional or sensory quality. Further studies should explore the bioavailability of nutrients in fortified pap to assess its efficacy as a complementary food.

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